

Synthesis and spectral studies on transition metal complexes with 'Costa type' of ligands containing aromatic motifs

K. Hussain Reddy* and M. Radhakrishna Reddy

Department of Chemistry, Sri Krishnadevaraya University, Anantapur-515 003, India

Fax : 091-08554-29043

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Macrocyclic nickel(II) and copper(II) complexes have been prepared using preformed ligands, viz. bis(diacetylmonoxime)-1,2-phenylenediimine and bis(diacetylmonoxime)-3,4-tolylenediimine. ESR spectral data of copper complexes suggest that the unpaired electron lies predominantly in the $d_{x^2-y^2}$ orbital. Various electronic and ESR parameters have been calculated and discussed. Electrochemical behavior of these complexes has been investigated by cyclic voltammetry.

Costa type¹ of ligands derived using diacetylmonoxime and aliphatic diamines have been frequently employed for the preparation of cobalt complexes (to derive model compounds for vitamin B₁₂)². However, metal complexes with costa type of ligands containing aromatic motifs are scarce. Recently we have reported³ organometal complexes with these modified ligands. We report herein the synthesis, characterization, spectral and electrochemical studies on macrocyclic nickel(II) and copper(II) complexes of bis(diacetylmonoxime)-1,2-phenylenediimine, (DOH)₂Pn and bis(diacetylmonoxime)-3,4-tolylenediimine, (DOH)₂Tn.

Results and Discussion

All the complexes (Table 1) are stable at room temperature, non-hygroscopic, insoluble in water and readily soluble in methanol, ethanol, DMF and DMSO. The molar conductivity data ($1.5\text{--}2.4 \Omega^{-1} \text{cm}^2 \text{mol}^{-1}$) suggest that the complexes are non-electrolytes.

Table 1. Analytical data of nickel and copper complexes (1-4)*

Compd. no.	Molecular formula	Colour	M.p. °C
1	[Ni(C ₁₄ H ₁₇ N ₄ O ₂)(Cl)(H ₂ O)]	Reddish brown	280d
2	[Cu(C ₁₄ H ₁₇ N ₄ O ₂)(Cl)(H ₂ O)]	Greenish black	310d
3	[Ni(C ₁₅ H ₁₉ N ₄ O ₂)(Cl)(H ₂ O)]	Reddish brown	290d
4	[Cu(C ₁₅ H ₁₉ N ₄ O ₂)(Cl)(H ₂ O)]	Greenish black	209-211

*All compounds gave satisfactory C, H and N analyses.

Magnetic susceptibility and electronic spectra :

The magnetic moments of 1 and 3 (2.91 and 3.32 B.M.) are indicative of octahedral structure for nickel(II) complexes. The magnetic moments of the copper(II) complexes 2 and 4 (1.69 and 1.72 B.M.) correspond to the presence of one unpaired electron.

- 1 R = H, M = Ni
- 2 R = H, M = Cu
- 3 R = CH₃, M = Ni
- 4 R = CH₃, M = Cu

The electronic spectra (DMF) of nickel(II) complexes 1 and 3 exhibit three bands at 9950, 10582; 16129, 17699; 27397, 23810 cm^{-1} , assigned to ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{2g}(F)$, ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(F)$ and ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(P)$ transitions, respectively, as expected for octahedral geometry. The spectral parameters like ligand field splitting energy ($10 Dq$), Racah inter-electronic repulsion parameter (B), covalent factor (B_{35}) and ligand field stabilization energy (LFSE) are presented in Table 2. The B and B_{35} values have been calculated for nickel complexes following standard equations⁴. The B_{35} values obtained for the present complexes are less than unity suggesting considerable amount of covalent character of the metal-ligand bonds. The electronic spectra of copper(II) complexes 2 and 4 in DMF show a broad maxima at 16230 and 17479 cm^{-1} , respectively, with a shoulder on the low energy side at 13650 and 15625 cm^{-1} , respectively, suggesting that these complexes have distorted octahedral structure. In addition, another band observed above 24000 cm^{-1} is assigned to charge transfer transitions⁵.

Table 2. Electronic spectral data and ligand field parameters of nickel complexes 1 and 3

Compd. no.	Method	ν_1 cm ⁻¹	ν_2 cm ⁻¹	ν_3 cm ⁻¹	B	B_{35}^*	$\delta\nu^{**}$	$10Dq$	$\nu_2-\nu_1$	ν_2/ν_1	LFSE kcal mol ⁻¹
1	Obs.	9950	16129	27397	—	—	—	9950	6179	1.62	28.4
	calcd.	$10Dq$	13929	29601	912	0.86	-2204	9950	3979	1.40	—
3	Obs.	10582	17699	23810	—	—	—	10582	7117	1.67	30.2
	Calcd.	$10Dq$	13125	28387	651	0.62	-4577	10582	2543	1.24	—

*Ratio of the free ion and of the complex. **Difference in the observed and calculated value of frequencies.

IR spectra :

The broad band of medium intensity observed at 2900 cm⁻¹ in the free ligands shifted to ~2400 cm⁻¹ in all the complexes. This is attributable to the ν_{OH} of hydrogen bond⁶. Strong bands of medium intensity appeared in the ligands (DOH)₂Pn and (DOH)₂Tn at 1584 and 1576 cm⁻¹ are shifted ($\Delta\nu = 14-20$ cm⁻¹) to lower wavenumber, suggesting the participation of azomethine nitrogens in coordination. The appearance of only one band at 1220 cm⁻¹ in the free ligands shows that the two NOH groups are identical while the appearance of two bands at ~1220 and ~1090 cm⁻¹ accounts for two non-identical =N-O-linkages, C=N-O-H and C=N-O---H, in the complexes. The symmetric and asymmetric deformation vibrations of the methyl groups occur at 1370-1384 and 1449-1469 cm⁻¹, respectively. The water coordinated as a ligand to metal ions is recognized in their infrared spectra by the appearance of strong and broad absorption in the 3359-3474 cm⁻¹ region. Further, it is supported by the appearance of absorption signals around ~920 and ~750 cm⁻¹ due to rocking and wagging vibrations of coordinated water molecules. Bands at 422-428 cm⁻¹ are assigned to ν_{M-N} vibration.

ESR spectra :

The ESR spectra of complexes 2 and 4 were recorded in DMF at liquid nitrogen temperature. The spin-Hamiltonian, orbital reduction and bonding parameters of these complexes are given in Table 3. The g_{\parallel} and g_{\perp} values are computed from the spectra using tetracyanoethylene (TCNE) free radical as g -marker. The observed g_{\parallel} values for complexes 2 and 4 are less than 2.3, suggesting a significant covalent character of the metal-ligand bond in agreement to the previous observations. The higher g_{\parallel} values are due to higher elongation in the Z -axis of the complexes with $^2B_{1g}$ ground state. The quotient⁶ $g_{\parallel}/A_{\parallel}$ is empirically treated as a measure of the distortion from planarity. The range of g/A values (158 and 171 cm⁻¹) for the present copper(II) chelates clearly indicates a strong octahedral distortion. The calculated G

Table 3. Spin-Hamiltonian and orbital reduction parameters of copper complexes 2 and 4

Parameter	2	4
g_{\parallel}	2.292	2.306
g_{\perp}	2.093	2.099
g_{av}	2.160	2.168
G	3.210	3.140
A_{\parallel}^*	0.0134	0.0146
A_{\perp}^*	0.0032	0.0034
A_{av}^*	0.0066	0.0077
K_{\parallel}	0.932	1.050
K_{\perp}	1.041	0.930
α^2	0.556	0.558
P	0.0191	0.0216
K	0.2823	0.31

*Units in cm⁻¹.

values for the complexes 2 and 4 are found to be 3.14 and 3.21, respectively, indicating a small exchange interaction between copper centres. The α^2 values for these complexes suggest the presence of covalent bonding in them.

Cyclic voltammetric studies :

The cyclic voltammograms for the complexes were recorded in DMF containing 0.1 M TBAClO₄ supporting electrolyte with a three-electrode assembly (glassy carbon working electrode, platinum wire as auxiliary electrode and Ag/AgCl reference electrode) at 25°.

The CVs of complexes 1 and 3 show only one irreversible reduction wave at $E_{pc} = -1.38$ V. Other waves are poorly defined and are hidden in large background current. The CVs of copper complexes 2 and 4 show single reduction wave at the $E_{1/2} = 0.50$ and 0.52 V, respectively. The reversible couple is assigned to $Cu^{2+} \rightleftharpoons Cu^+$ couple. The differences between the cathodic and anodic peaks (ΔE) of complexes 2 and 4 are 100 and 170 mV, respectively. It is suggested that the electron transfer is much faster in complex 2 compared to 4. The $E_{1/2}$ values

for the present copper complexes are similar to the values reported earlier⁷.

Experimental

All the solvents used were of A.R. grade. Nickel(II) chloride, copper(II) chloride, 1,2-diaminobenzene and 3,4-diaminotoluene (Fluka AG) and diacetylmonoxime (Spectrochem, A.R.) were used. Synthesis of ligands and instruments used are described elsewhere^{8,9}.

Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} complexes : The reaction mixture containing ligand (0.02 mol) and metal salt (0.02 mol) in acetone (30 cm³) was refluxed with stirring for 2 h. The resulted coloured solution was filtered and kept overnight at room temperature. The dark coloured compound which separated out was filtered and washed repeatedly with acetone followed by diethyl ether.

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